

Differences in root volume of selected upland and lowland rice varieties

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Refined selection techniques that offer greater precision in screening for drought resistance are needed to assess the avoidance and tolerance mechanisms that operate at different growth stages.

High root volume indicates that a plant can permeate a large volume of soil or that it has a high proportion of thick roots. Theoretically, such a plant would have greater water-gathering potential for growth and survival.

We investigated differences in root volume among upland and lowland rice varieties and compared aboveground characters that might be associated with high root volume.

Thirteen test varieties identified in mass field screening to have varying reactions to drought were grown in an aeroponic culture system. The trial was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Root volume was determined by displacement of water in a 1-liter graduated cylinder 44 d after seed soaking. Other root and shoot characters also were measured.

Test varieties differed appreciably in root volume. Rikuto Norin 21, a Japanese upland variety, had the greatest root volume; IR20, a semi-dwarf drought-susceptible lowland variety, the least (Table 1). Upland varieties in general had greater root

Table 1. Mean root volume of 13 rice varieties 44 d after seed soaking, and field reaction to drought. IRRRI, 1989.

Variety	Type of culture ^a	Mean volume ^b (ml)	Drought reaction ^c	
			Vegetative phase	Reproductive phase
Rikuto Norin	U	31 a	3	5
Kalakeri	U	30 ab	7	5
BPI-76	RL	26 abc	3	—
Moroberekan	U	23 a-d	5	3
Guang-Mao 127	RL	22 bcd	—	—
Dular	DP	21 cde	5	3
Kinandang Patong	U	21 cde	3	3
Salumpikit	U	16 def	4	6
Taichung Native 1	IL	15 def	6	9
Mahsuri	RL	14 def	5	9
Palawan	U	14 def	4	—
IR8	IL	13 ef	4	9
IR20	IL	10 f	7	9

^aU = upland, RL = rainfed lowland, IL = improved lowland, DP = dual purpose. ^bMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^c1 = resistant, 9 = susceptible.

volumes than lowland varieties. Among the lowland varieties, BPI-76 had a greater root volume than drought-resistant check Moroberekan. (BPI-76 was moderately resistant to field drought in upland mass screening nurseries.)

Root volume was negatively associated with reproductive phase drought reaction (-0.85**): varieties showing high drought resistance had greater root volumes than susceptible varieties.

Interactions among plant characters are important in determining appropriate indices to select for drought resistance. Associations between root volume and root or shoot characters were positive except for tiller number (Table 2). The only significant correlations, however, were between root volume and root length and between root volume and shoot length.

Table 2. Relationship between root volume and 7 root or shoot characters of 13 test varieties. IRRRI, 1989.

Character	<i>r</i>
Root volume vs	
Root length	0.86589**
Root diameter	0.43166 ^{ns}
Root number	0.11297 ^{ns}
Root/shoot ratio	0.48075 ^{ns}
Shoot length	0.68428**
Tiller number	-0.08742 ^{ns}
Leaf number	0.00738 ^{ns}

In earlier studies, root length was correlated positively with shoot length. Thus, tall plants should have deep roots and large root volumes. Plant height could then be a useful criterion for selecting progenies with deep root systems and high root volume, especially for resistance to drought during the reproductive phase. ■

Variation in chlorophyll content of rice flag leaf lamina and sheath

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The chlorophyll content of the lamina, sheath, and exposed internode indicates the photosynthetic potential of these organs. One may conceptualize a

rice ideotype whose enhanced photosynthetic potential of the flag leaf lamina, leaf sheath, exposed internode, and panicle allows significant reduction in the size of leaf blades, without reducing the plant's assimilatory potential. Such a plant type could be suitable for high density planting and high fertilizer N application.

In 1989 dry season, we studied variation in chlorophyll content of the flag leaf lamina and sheath of five rice

varieties of similar flowering duration (group 1). A chlorophyll meter (Minolta SPAD 502) was used to measure chlorophyll values at heading for flag leaf blade and sheath from the main culms of 10 plants/variety per three replications.

IR47686-6-2-2-1 had the highest chlorophyll content in the flag leaf blade (Table 1). Suweon 290 had the highest chlorophyll content in the sheath.